

Early Ahmarian Lithic Techno-Economy and Mobility at Al-Ansab 1, Wadi Sabra, Southern Jordan

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ABSTRACT

Al-Ansab 1 is a stratified Early Ahmarian site of unusual preservation, extent and occupational intensity close to a high-quality raw material outcrop. The site is located in the Upper Wadi Sabra in the Greater Petra Area, Southern Jordan. This paper presents the results of a detailed raw material, technology and curation study of the lithic material from the 2009 to 2011 field campaigns at Al-Ansab 1. The lithic technology from the site is well-defined, relatively homogeneous, and oriented towards the production of regular, narrow and pointed laminar blanks, which are preferentially transformed into el-Wad points. The assemblage attests to an integrated production system, yielding blanks of varied morphotechnical characteristics at various stages of the reduction process to supply a diversified toolkit. Raw material exploitation focuses on locally available raw materials and is generally expedient. Tool shares are low, and modification tends to be marginal and minimally invasive. Curation analysis of the lithic toolkit suggests that most tools exhibit limited use-lives and were only moderately resharpened. Combined with a high investment in core preparation, maintenance, and blank predetermination evident in operational chains, this qualifies the Early Ahmarian at Al-Ansab 1 as a blank production economy (*économie du débitage*). This status entails particular consequences for economization and planning and is grounded in a strong convergence between blank production and tool design. Al-Ansab 1 provides insights into the exceptional residential mobility of Early Ahmarian foragers and showcases the importance of localities close to predictable key resources in the Southern Levant.

Keywords: Early Upper Paleolithic; Eastern Mediterranean; lithic technology; raw material economy; operational chain; curation; mobility

כלכלת הצור ודגמי התנועה באתר האחמרי הקדום אנסב 1, ואדי סברה, ירדן

חנה פרו-סושון

תקציר עברי

מקובל שתעשיית הצור של ציידי ולקטי התרבות האחמרית הקדומה משקפת אורח חיים נוודי ביותר. האתר אנסב 1, באזור מען שבדרום ירדן, הוא מקרה מבחן שממנו ניתן ללמוד מהם התהליכים השונים המשפיעים על אורחות החיים. המחקר מתבסס על בדיקה מפורטת של הצור הגולמי, שחזור רצף הפעולות ודרך בחירת הכלים ושימורם. הערכת תהליכי ייצור כלי הצור התבססה על ניתוח מאפייני הפריטים, הגדרת השלבים ברצף הפעולות וסוג חומר הגלם. האתר נמצא בנקודה הסמוכה ביותר למקור המים ולמחשופי חומר הגלם. רוב הצור הגולמי מקורו במחשוף הצור הקרוב לאתר, ומיעוטו יובא. בחירת תרכיזי הצור הייתה בררנית והשפעת סוג חומר הגלם על תהליך ההתזה הייתה מועטה. במבחנים סטטיסטיים שנועדו להשוות בין השלבים השונים של רצף הפעולות נמצאו הבדלים מובהקים באורך הפריטים שהופקו. בהתזת חומר הגלם האימוני הגס בולט שינוי בסוג המקבת, או באופי ההכאה, בין שלבי ההתחלה לשלבי הסיום של רצף ההפחתה. רוב הכלים נוצרו לשימוש קצר וניתן להוכיח שרק מעטים מהם – נקרים ופריטים קטומים – הועברו למקומות אחרים. ניצול רוב הגרעינים היה בזבזני ולעיתים קרובות הם נזרקו בשל טעויות התזה. מעטים הגרעינים שנוצלו באופן אינטנסיבי, ומעטים יותר הם אלה בהם ניכרות פעולות שנועדו לאפשר את ניצולם המירבי. נראה שערכת הכלים הייתה קלת משקל וכללה חודי אל וואד, נקרים, פריטים קטומים, להבי מטרה ומספר גרעינים.

הטיפול בחומרי הגלם ובכלים היה בזבזני אך עקרונית ההפקה נשמרו היטב. זה נראה סותר את הידוע על ניידות בפרהיסטוריה; טיפול בזבזני בחומרי גלם וכלים מלמד על ניידות מעטה, בעוד ההקפדה יוצאת הדופן על דרך סיתות הגרעינים מצביעה על ניידות רבה. נראה שלאנסב 1 הגיעו פעמים רבות כדי להשיג צור גולמי. זהו אחד מאתרי מערך יישובי מגורים, כזה האופייני לאזור הלבנט הממוזג ששימש מקום מקלט מהקרחתונים. בהשוואה כללית נראה שמערך אתרי המגורים בלבנט היה מיושב יותר ממקביליו הבין-קרחוניים/בין-סטאדיאליים באירופה המרכזית (התרבות האזילית, התקופה המסוליתית). גורם חריג שאינו מתאים למודל המוצע הוא ההקפדה של אנשי הלבנט על עקרונית סיתות הגרעין בהשוואה למלקטי המזון ואוגרי המזון באירופה המרכזית, כמו אנשי התרבות המגדלנית. נראה שההסבר לשונות טמון בגורמים תרבותיים כמו מערכת המושגים ובדרישות השימוש בחודי צור ככלי נשק.

INTRODUCTION

The Early Ahmarian is the first fully-developed Early Upper Paleolithic technocomplex in the Levant (Gilead 1991; Schyle 1992; Coinman and Henry 1995; Coinman 2000; Saca 2002; Phillips and Saca 2003; Goring-Morris and Belfer-Cohen 2003; Shea 2013: 152; Hauck 2015; Belfer-Cohen and Goring-Morris 2017, Goring-Morris and Belfer-Cohen 2018; Richter et al. 2020). It has been defined only forty years ago (Gilead 1981; Marks 1981), giving rise to the so-called 'Two Tradition' model of socio-technical evolution for the region. Archaeological sites attributed to the Early Ahmarian span across the entire Levantine corridor focusing on the marginal zone (Jones et al. 1983; Marks 1983; Schyle 1992; Gilead and Bar-Yosef 1993; Saca 2002; Hauck 2015; Kadowaki et al. 2015; Goring-Morris and Belfer-Cohen 2018). Early Ahmarian assemblages have been studied by various authors and research groups (e.g. Bar-Yosef and Belfer 1977; Marks 1977, 1983; Jones et al. 1983; Phillips 1987, 1988; Gilead 1991; Monigal 2003; Fox and Coinman 2004; Kuhn 2004; Goring-Morris and Davidzon 2006; Kuhn et al. 2009; Schyle 2015a; Richter et al. 2020; Abulafia et al. 2021) and the technological and typological signature of this Early Upper Paleolithic entity is now comparatively well-documented (Davidzon and Goring-Morris 2003; Monigal 2003; Goring-Morris and Davidzon 2006; Hussain 2015; Abulafia et al. 2021; Parow-Souchon 2020). The Early Ahmarian is now recognized to entail a macro-regional division between a 'Northern' and 'Southern' variant with important differences in technology and possibly ecology (e.g. Hauck 2015; Kadowaki et al. 2015).

However, what is currently understood to a lesser extent are the techno-economic principles and mobility strategies underpinning Early Ahmarian spatial behavior, especially the interaction between raw material acquisition and transport, tool curation and adopted technological concepts. The present study attempts to fill this gap. It examines the raw material ecology and operational chains documented at the stratified and well-preserved Early Ahmarian

site of Al-Ansab 1, District Ma'an, Southern Jordan, to better characterize and understand the relationship between raw materials, lithic technologies, and human settlement dynamics.

Our study proceeds in five steps. We first situate our approach in the broader theoretical landscape of Paleolithic stone artifact analysis, outlining our understanding of technology and its relationship with mobility, raw material provisioning, economization and curation. We then briefly describe the principal methods employed in this study and present the results of our techno-economic analysis. In the last step, we draw together the available evidence and discuss the basic principles guiding techno-economy and mobility at Al-Ansab 1. In addition, we situate our results in the broader context of the Early Ahmarian and outline future research possibilities in the comparative study of Pleistocene mobility and land-use systems.

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

Technology as system

Human technology is a multi-dimensional phenomenon comprising technical objects and artifacts, along with actions and action-plans, know-how, skill, and conceptual resources (Pelegriin 1988, 1995; Schlanger 1990; Boëda 1994, 2005, 2013; Inizan et al. 1999; Ploux and Karlin 2014). There are two definitions of technology that currently underpin the lithic discourse in Palaeolithic archaeology. This first definition foregrounds social and cognitive factors of technical practice, emphasizing the anthropological and historical status of human technologies (Gille 1978; Lemonnier 1986, 2012; Pfaffenberger 1992; Schlanger 1994; Dobres and Hoffman 1994; Sigaut 2012). The second definition of technology accentuates the ecological, material and instrumental qualities of technologies (Binford 1962; Jochim 1981; Torrence 1989; Bousman 1993; Kuhn 1993, 1995; Kelly 2014). The 'Cognitive Science of Technology' recently proposed by Stout (2021) seeks to integrate both research angles within the framework of cultural evolutionary theory.

Technologies inescapably bear witness to some purpose, intention or design and exhibit broader functionalities (e.g. Bleed 1986; Bamforth 1991) – they yield system ‘finalities’ (Valentin 1995; Pelegrin 2011). Yet, as being in part material constructs, technologies are not merely passive entities. They set limits to human action and actively influence the cultural horizons, decisions and perceptions of their makers and users (Leroi-Gourhan 1964; Sigaut 2012). The material, social and cognitive affordances provided by technology in turn help to understand how technologies and artifacts mediate, and frequently co-determine, human behavior and evolution (Sinclair 2014; cf. Faraj and Azad 2012). Technologies are both constituted and constituting – they are brought into existence by human action but simultaneously shape human sociocultural realities and long-term developments (Hussain and Will 2021). The notion of ‘technicity’ (Stiegler 1994; Kinsley 2014) – emphasizing the co-shaping of humans and their technological worlds – encapsulates this emerging view of human-technology relations (Sigaut 2012; Hussain 2018).

Technology can be studied from many different perspectives but it is always more than the sum of its material artifacts. We here adopt a system-level approach in which technology is considered the product of interactions between heterogeneous structural components including but not limited to material artifacts. This approach places emphasis on the organization of technical relationships and the character of the involved technical processes (cf. Pelegrin et al. 1988; Inizan et al. 1999; Schmid 2020). In addition, the approach draws attention to system-level performance characteristics – operational qualities of technological systems as a whole – that result from distinct operational sequences involving aspects of acquisition, preparation, production and use. Some of these intra-system relationships can be quantified, while others require qualitative description and interpretation (Hussain 2019).

Techno-economy

A systemic understanding of technology implies that economy is a performance characteristic of technological systems as a whole. Economic questions can therefore be asked with regard to varying components of the system as well as different domains of technology (e.g. raw material management, production and tool-use), but also in terms of the global articulation of these components or domains and their trade-offs (Perlès 1987; Geneste 1991). In the context of lithic technology, raw material choice and nodule morphology can constrain the possibilities and effectiveness of core preparation and thus impact the relationship between produced blanks and required tools, for example forcing hominins to invest more into blank transformation, tool production and tool maintenance. Reduction strategies can take advantage of raw material qualities or ensure the morphotechnical differentiation of produced blanks, so that blank configurations broadly anticipate blank selection and tool manufacture decision (cf. Hussain and Will 2021). Initial raw material morphologies may also interact with reduction strategies to produce inverse relationships between blank productivity and the transformative potential of produced blanks as well as the depth and complexity of tool biographies (cf. Bourguignon et al. 2006; Delagnes and Rendu 2011). The serial production of raw material-conserving lightweighted blanks of similar morphologies is for example often tied to stable tool forms with reduced investment in their manufacture and maintenance, while the production of thick and chunky blanks of various configurations frequently leads to unstable tool forms which are constantly resharped and reworked (cf. e.g. Weißmüller 2003). Toolkit diversification, and especially the conjunction of ‘domestic’ (e.g. endscraper, burin) and ‘non-domestic’ (e.g. points, hunting/butchery knives, weapon inserts) tools (definitions following Tartar et al. 2005; Bon 2005), can thus be an important locus of economic system-level functioning.

Economic strategies of raw material acquisition, core exploitation, blank selection and tool-use are almost always interlaced with the system-wide organization of technical actions as well as the structure and internal trade-offs of the involved operational sequences. It follows that lithic economy cannot be meaningfully studied without a detailed reconstruction of lithic

production technologies and their consequences for raw material provisioning and tool use. The here adopted approach recognizes this reciprocal interaction of technology and economy and is accordingly labelled ‘techno-economic’.

Mobility and provisioning

Economic dimensions of lithic technology are often studied in relation to settlement patterns and past human landuse as mobility is widely regarded to act as a key interface between human and environmental systems (Kelly 1988, 1992; Torrence 1989; Bousman 1993; Baales 1996; Richter 1997, 2018; Uthmeier 2004; Kuhn et al. 2016: Fig. 1). While the relationship between technology and mobility has been examined from varying viewpoints and theoretical angles – e.g. cultural ecology (Binford 1962, 1972; Butzer 1971; Jochim 1998), human behavioral ecology (Winterhalder and Smith 2000; Shea 2011) and what is known as the ‘technological organization’ approach in the Anglophone literature (Shott 1986; Nelson 1991; McCall 2015) – there is a broad consensus, promoted by seminal ethnoarchaeological work (Binford 1977, 1980, 1982; Yellen 1977; Cashdan 1984), that the economics of mobility are an important determinant of lithic technological organization and design. The economics of mobility for example include strategic considerations and decisions related to transportation costs and benefits, the availability and predictability of key resources such as animal game and raw material as well as their distribution in the landscape (Kelly 1983, 1995; Torrence 1989; Kent 1992; Bousman 1993; Habu and Fitzhugh 2002).

For nomadic hunter-gatherers, Binford (1980) distinguished between ‘forager’ and ‘collector’ adaptations with distinct mobility tendencies (logistical vs. residential), and hence specific techno-economic requirements and constraints. Foragers are conducive to social fission-and-fusion dynamics, tend to rely on short-term task-specific camps and are mostly

found in temperate, forested environments, while collectors typically move as a social unit, depend on more stable basecamps and tend to inhabit periglacial/arctic, open steppe environments (1980, 2001; Habu and Fitzhugh 2002; Uthmeier 2004: 321). The two prototypes can further be qualified in terms of their ‘dislocation frequency’ and ‘mobility distance’ (Table 1). Logistical foragers exhibit low dislocation frequency due to the anchoring role of stable basecamps but basecamp moves can cover considerable distances of up to 300 km or more (cf. Weniger 1982; Floss 1994; Kuhn 2004) and are often connected to the availability of specific resources such as migrating herds of reindeer (Baales 1996). Residential collectors, by contrast, tend to display elevated dislocation frequencies due to high-interval relocation moves and relatively short-term presence in a given area, but mobility distances can be extremely short, for example when ‘mapping’ widely available but scattered and quickly exhausted resource patches on the landscape (Binford 1980: 5).

Table 1. Comparison of subsistence systems in forest and steppe biotopes (modified after Uthmeier 2004: 322; Floss 1994: 334–335).

Characteristics of the economic and subsistence system	Biotope/Environment	
	Forest	Steppe
Residential mobility ("macro moves") - dislocation frequency - mobility distance	high low	low high
Logistical mobility ("micro moves")	low	high
Size of annual foraging range	small to medium	medium to large
Subsistence stress	high	low
Relative cost of raw material acquisition	low (due to small distances at high residential mobility)	high (due to large distances and phases dominated by subsistence tasks)
Time available to produce and test gear	short	long
Quality of gear	minimal	optimal
Time for experimenting	short	long

Focusing on raw material ecologies, Kuhn (1992, 1995, 2004) expanded on these insights, suggesting that the availability of tools in situations where ‘it would not otherwise be possible to have them’ (Kuhn 1995: 21) would constitute another regulating factor for lithic techno-economies. He distinguished between two general options to meet such challenges and identified three specific strategies to cope with tool supply: People can modulate their basic toolmaking behaviors (expedient/reactive vs. curated/proactive) or they may adopt provisioning strategies that either centre on individuals, places or activities. On the basic level, tools can be made from whatever raw material is available, so that tool forms and production technologies are adapted to local lithologies, involve little to no transportation costs and tools can be quickly discarded (expediency); alternatively, people may ‘care for their tools and toolkits’ (Nelson 1991: 62), transport them over considerable distances, rework, repair and recycle them and carefully select the worked raw material (curation).

Technological provisioning describes different ways to anticipate and mitigate future raw material shortages. One possibility is to directly supply individuals with durable objects that ensure sufficient cutting-edge availability over extended periods, either by supplying them with enough tools (‘personal gear’ sensu Binford 1977) or by providing them with cores or recyclable tools (provisioning of individuals: Kuhn 1995: 22–23). The second option is to furnish particular localities and sites with raw material or reusable tools (provisioning of places: Kuhn 1995, 2020: 70). The third option, finally, is the provisioning of activities in relation to specific raw material sources or plentiful primary raw material outcrops (Kuhn 2004). These three provisioning strategies come with different sets of testable predictions. For example, individual provisioning is expected to yield balanced assemblages of finished and curated domestic and non-domestic tools, whereas place provisioning should be associated with many heavily reduced cores and reusable blanks; activity provisioning, conversely, is predicated upon expedient tool production or highly specialized tool-task profiles.

Foundational work on lithic knapping economies (Inizan 1976, 1980; Perlès 1980, 1991) and more recent studies on blank-tool interaction (Boëda 1997, 2013; Soriano 2000; Pelegrin 2011) have similarly shown that blank production and tool technologies co-configure each other and their interaction has important economic implications. To ensure a supply of diversified toolkits anticipating situationally varying exigencies is considered to be an essential economic problem in this work as well. Perlès (1980, 1991) identified two sets of two strategies that are available to knappers to address this basic issue: First, knappers may ensure toolkit diversification by differentiated raw material selection, acquisition and exploitation (*économie de la matière première*) or by the differential organization of knapping (*économie de débitage*). Second, knappers may either employ multiple lithic reduction systems to foster a differentiated repertoire of blanks (segregated production) – each system then tends to yield a distinct set of usable blanks – or they may organize knapping operations within a single system in such a way that the operational sequence generates different blanks at different reduction stages or from different core locations (integrated production).

Modification strategies can be analyzed along similar lines: Retouch may be adapted to different blank shapes – and thus follow the lead of blanks – or it may substantially alter their original morphology. Retouch intentionalities vary in conjunction with these available options: They either seek to stabilize, normalize or standardize particular morphotechnical features inherited from blank production, or they may fabricate features previously not found on these blanks and thus create tool functionalities only weakly related or entirely unrelated to blank production outcomes. We can expect that production systems that yield well-differentiated spectra of blank forms are prone to support blank-tool coherence and rely less on invasive retouch modalities. Importantly, the solution to problems of cutting-edge supply is not found in provisioning or mobility strategies then, but derives from the organization of lithic knapping itself. The relationship between domestic and hunting-related tools is consequently yet another critical locus of lithic techno-economy (Bon 2005; Pelegrin 2011; Hussain 2015).

Multilevel curation and tool design

A system-level approach to lithic techno-economy requires a few clarifications with regard to curation and the principles of tool design. Curation has traditionally been defined as a set of specific strategies for tool manufacture, use and maintenance (Binford 1979; Bamforth 1986; Nahler 1991; Nelson 1991; Shott 1995; Clark and Barton 2017; see above), but this somewhat narrow understanding is gratuitous and can be broadened to also include other technological domains and operational stages. There are then at least three levels of curational behavior that can be distinguished: 1) raw material procurement and exploitation; 2) blank production technology; 3) structure and design of tools and toolkits. Raw material curation is for example reflected in patterned differences between the management of local and non-local raw materials (definitions are given below when the methods of raw material analysis are described). ‘Caring for’ particular raw materials leads to monospecific raw material assemblages and highly reduced raw material volumes with production technologies taking advantage of the target raw material qualities and morphologies. Curated blank production technologies are characterized by heightened investment in initial core preparation and are often concerned with blank control and standardization, typically requiring continuous and highly formalized core maintenance procedures (e.g. crested blades, core tablets). Some of these interrelationships also inform the argument by Wallace and Shea (2006) on the structural linkage between mobility, curation and technological pre-determination. Tool curation, finally, can simply be measured as the intensity of tool reduction (Dibble 1987, 1995; Kuhn 1990; Hiscock and Clarkson 2005), or, alternatively, as the potential length of tool life-cycles and the structural possibilities to resharpen or co-opt them for unanticipated functions.

The second, strictly technological understanding of tool curation draws attention to the structural dynamics of tool reduction and the investment into tool upkeep, including specifically devised strategies to prolonging life-histories and avoiding functional exhaustion (Uthmeier

2011). On a basic level, we can discriminate between fully shaped, partially shaped and edge-near modified tools as well as unmodified tools including used plain blanks (cf. Hahn 1991; Richter 1990, 1997; Weißmüller 1995; Uthmeier 2004). Shaped tools tend to be associated with increased investment in tool construction and often exhibit extended and complex biographies paired with evidence for distinct resharpening patterns (e.g. tranchet blow; cf. Soriano 2000). Edge-near modified tools are generally less curated but important distinctions can be made with respect to the type, coverage and intensity of retouch. Curation here is linked to broader modification strategies and retouch intentions discussed above. In Upper Palaeolithic assemblages edge-modified pieces can further be subdivided into varied pieces with lateral retouch and well-defined ‘working’ (Uthmeier 2004) or ‘business’ ends (Kuhn 2020) which are normally found on the narrow terminations of the blank (proximal, distal), mostly of domestic tools, and yield different potentials and options for curation. Unmodified yet nonetheless utilized blanks indicate expedient tool-use since tool-use is fully adapted to the blank matrices in question and exploits their functional affordances.

Tool curation can further be assessed with regard to what Weißmüller (1995, 2003) has called ‘final’ and ‘transient’ forms (cf. Uthmeier 2004). Final tool forms possess a clearly defined, stable morphology and their form is linked to a specific function or operational principle which tends to be preserved over the life-cycle. Final tool forms are quickly discarded and replaced when they break and are characterized by typological stability. Transient or transitional tool forms, to the contrary, change their morphology in the course of their use-life and are subjected to structural changes altering or preserving their functions. True transient forms are characterized by specific morphologies linked to particular reduction/resharpening stages (e.g. Dibble 1987), while weakly transient forms retain their basic structure but are nonetheless repaired. Transient forms such as bifaces and recurrently reworked sidescrapers but also weakly transient forms such as multi-burins or double endscrapers and especially ‘combination tools’ are often notorious to classify and display elevated typological fluidity.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The site of Al-Ansab 1

Research background and previous studies

Surveys and excavations in the Al-Ansab area were conducted in the framework of the Collaborative Research Centre (CRC) 806 ‘Our Way to Europe’ from 2009 to 2019. Building on the notion of ‘contextual areas’ developed by Richter and colleagues (2012), the goal was to elucidate and map the varied environmental contexts of early anatomically modern human settlement outside of Africa, mostly based on freshwater lake sediments and terrestrial archives. These environmental archives are then contextualized and compared with regional technological signatures observed in the archaeological record (Bertrams et al. 2012; Schyle and Richter 2015; Richter et al. 2020). ‘Contextual areas’ are understood here as spaces ‘of systemic coherence at a given time span and within natural boundaries relevant to human adaptation’ (Richter et al. 2012). Such areas help to understand and compare human-environment interactions in the Early Upper Paleolithic and the trajectories and dynamics of human settlement consolidation in the Eastern Mediterranean Levant.

The Jordan Rift Valley is a natural corridor, a geophysical guideline and attractor of human mobility, and delineates the northbound route from north–east Africa and the Sinai peninsula to Western Eurasia (e.g. Bar-Yosef 1987; Goren-Inbar and Speth 2004; Vaks et al. 2007; Beyin 2011; Frumkin et al. 2011; Richter et al. 2012). The Wadi Sabra in the Greater Petra Area is a promising research area because of its location close to this prominent south–north trajectory, its well-preserved MIS 3–2 sediments (Schyle and Uerpmann 1988; Schyle 2015b), and its great potential for geoarchaeological research in terrestrial sediments and nearby freshwater lakes (Richter et al. 2012, 2015; Miebach et al. 2019).

Al-Ansab 1 is the hitherto best documented and most comprehensively studied, stratified archaeological site in the Wadi Sabra (Richter et al. 2020). Sedimentological and

geochemical analyses were conducted by Bertrams (2013, 2015; Bertrams et al. 2012) and the rich lithic assemblages from the site have been studied by Schyle (2015a), Hussain (2015) Parow-Souchon (2020), and most recently Gennai (2021). The Al-Ansab 1 assemblage was placed into the wider context of the Levantine Early Ahmarian by Hauck (2015; cf. Richter et al. 2020). Richter et al. (2020) studied the spatial and geoarchaeological integrity of the site and Parow-Souchon (2020) compared it to other Upper Paleolithic occurrences in the Wadi Sabra area. Al-Ansab 1 has been dated both by thermoluminescence and radiocarbon to between ca. 38 and 31 ka cal. BP (Klasen et al. 2013; Richter et al. 2020).

Site location, topography and stratigraphy

The Al-Ansab locality is situated at an altitude of 610 m above sea level in the southern part of the Wadi Sabra (Schyle and Uerpmann 1988; Richter et al. 2015; Parow-Souchon 2020; Fig. 1). The site of Al-Ansab 1 is located on top of a steep sediment remnant, 20 m above the current wadi channel at the junction of the Wadi Sabra and a smaller tributary, the eponymous Wadi Al-Ansab (Fig. 2). A steep flint-carrying limestone ridge protects the back of the sediment remnant to the north and thus shields it from erosion (Bertrams 2013: 35; Schyle 2015b). Some 100 m to the east of the stratified archaeological site, a freshwater spring provides clean drinking water, along with shallow pools of standing water upstream and a notable strip of moisture at the right bank of the wadi channel (Richter et al. 2020).

<<Figure 1>>

Currently, the water table in the wider region is low in comparison to Pleistocene and early Holocene conditions (Bartov et al. 2003; Almogi-Labin et al. 2009; Torfstein et al. 2013; Bar-Matthews 2014; Miebach 2016; Stockhecke et al. 2016) mainly due to industrial water extraction activities (UN-ESCWA and BGR 2013; Bar-Matthews 2014). That the water table in the Ansab area is high even today suggests unusual freshwater availability in the past and

generally favorable conditions for human occupation. Al-Ansab 1 also harbors a high-quality flint outcrop and is located close to several other lower-quality raw material deposits (Fig. 3).

<<Figure 2>>

The main archaeological horizon of Al-Ansab 1 (Fig. 4) consists of highly consolidated, reddish-brown sands, including granules of quartz and weathered sandstone (Bertrams 2013: 44). The sands originate from colluvial (sheet-flow) and interlacing aeolian wadi sedimentation consolidated by a soil formation process associated with Upper Paleolithic human occupations (Bertrams et al. 2012). The excavated flint-bearing surface linked to the upper layer is almost perfectly horizontal and overlying gravel deposits are slightly curved following the current topography of the sediment remnant (Richter et al. 2015, 2020). The archaeological layer is exceptionally well-preserved, with a well-consolidated surface on top of a horizontal, 10 cm thick band of charcoal-rich sediment with numerous flint and limestone artifacts and a few poorly preserved faunal remains (Schyle 2015a; Parow-Souchon 2020). Large numbers of chips and the presence of the small lithic fraction attest to the primary position of the archaeological material. GIS-powered intra-site spatial analysis based on the complete excavated surface area (2015–2018) paired with a detailed examination of artifact orientation and the patterning of shallow pits and ash lenses in the excavated area support this conclusion and indicate the rapid burial of finds at Al-Ansab 1 (Richter et al. 2020; Schoenenberg 2018; Fig. 5).

<<Figure 3>>

<<Figure 4>><<Figure 5>>

Lithic artifacts

This study encompasses the lithic material recovered during the 2009–2011 excavation campaigns at Al-Ansab 1. Six square meters were excavated along a natural step in the topography (Fig. 4c), straightening the profile into the archaeological horizon. During these seasons, the primary focus was placed on collecting material from the artifact-bearing layer in

¼ m² units and dry-sieving the remaining sediment to acquire and document all small fraction material (Schyle 2015a, b). From these six m² a total of 9787 lithic items were recovered, and they form the basic sample for this study. The lithic material >0.5 cm, excluding chips and natural chunks, was then subjected to raw material and technological analyses described below.

Raw materials

The description and classification of exploited lithic raw materials form the baseline of subsequent technological analyses and provide key information on the lithic economy and raw material ecology at Al-Ansab 1. The adopted approach is inspired by transformation analysis (ger. Transformationsanalyse) as developed by Weißmüller (1995), Richter (1997), Pastoors (2001), Uthmeier (2004) and others (cf. Bataille 2020). This approach aims to elucidate differences and variations in the choice, exploitation, and transformation of lithic raw materials within and between lithic technologies, and to explore inter-assemblage variability from the perspective of technically mediated raw material management. The aim, however, is also to gain basic insights into the spatial and temporal fragmentation of lithic operational sequences, map raw material-related import/export dynamics as well as unravel the economic status and role of different raw materials (cf. Turq et al. 2013; Bataille 2020: 17–20). The foundation of the analysis is the reconstruction of raw material units (RMUs) on the basis of easily recognizable macroscopic features, such as color, structure and cortex. We distinguish between raw material groups (RMG) designating generic raw material occurrences in the landscape and smallest raw material entities (RME) grouping raw materials on the level of nodules (cf. Parow-Souchon and Heinen 2017).

Flint classification in this study was conducted both macroscopically and microscopically. It follows the Flint Raw Material Group (FRMG) system but are treated here as distinct raw material types, developed for the Neolithic of the Greater Petra Area (Gebel 1994; Muheisen et al. 2004; Purschwitz 2017; Parow-Souchon 2020, Parow-Souchon and

Purschwitz 2020). To facilitate the examination and comparison of raw material acquisition strategies, different FRMGs/raw material types associated with securely sourced geological formations are summarised on the basis of their outcrop attribution and assigned to newly constructed 'outcrop groups' (Fig. 6; cf. Fig. 7) which are used in this study as main proxy for the description of raw material procurement.

<<Figure 6>>

Lithic raw material availability in the Greater Petra Area is mainly bound to Eocene and Cretaceous geological formations. Five different geological units in the study area (cf. Fig. 6) might have acted as key sources for the different varieties of encountered prehistoric flints (from bottom to top): Na'ur Limestone (NL), Wadi as Sir Limestone (WSL), Wadi Umm Ghudran Limestone (WG), the undifferentiated Al-Hisa Phosphorite/Amman Silicified Limestone (AHP/ASL) and Umm Rijam Chert Limestone (URC; cf. Barjous 2003). These flint-bearing units are available as primary deposits along the escarpment of the Jordanian highlands, yielding fresh, high-quality flint raw material. The Umm Rijam Chert Limestone (URC) and Al-Hisa Phosphorite/Amman Silicified Limestone (AHP/ASL) formations are the richest and highest quality flint sources in the Greater Petra Area (Purschwitz 2017).

In the Wadi Sabra, flint can only be found in the immediate vicinity of the Al-Ansab locality, as tectonic processes have subsided and tilted Cretaceous and Eocene formations in the area. The site of Al-Ansab 1 is protected by a large ridge of URC-limestone, and a prominent cone-shaped hill from the same geological formation is located opposite the wadi channel (cf. Fig. 2 and 3). Furthermore, a large but heavily fractured AHP/ASL outcrop flanks the right side of the wadi in downstream direction. The embedded FRMGs and their associated formations have been summarized in Figure 7 to facilitate the comparison of source regions.

The URC material directly available at the Al-Ansab locality (FRMG 1, 5a, 5b, and 9) is subsumed under 'URC-Ansab'. Flint raw material groups attributed to the same formation, but not found directly at the Al-Ansab locality (FRMG 2, 3p, 4, and 6), are labelled 'URC-

General'. They can mainly be found in the highland escarpment and further to the north, in about nine hours walking distance, or ~13.5 km distance, from the site (cf. Fig. 6).

AHP/ASL (FRMG 3b, 3d and 11) as well as Silicified Limestone from the same geological formation (FRMG 10) are found in heavily fractured nodules at the Al-Ansab locality. In contrast to the outcrop directly at Al-Ansab, the flint from the same formation in the highland escarpment is of good quality and pristine preservation but derives from a source in about twelve hours walking distance (ca. 18 km) from the site (cf. Delage et al. 2020, Parow-Souchon and Purschwitz 2020). The material from the AHP/ASL formation correlates with the raw material documented in the Mishash formation found in Israel, colloquially also termed 'Chalcedony'.

The raw material group referred to as 'other sources' comprises flint varieties not found in the Greater Petra Area. Two categories of raw material acquisition distances are thus documented at Al-Ansab 1: Acquisition centered on the site or its immediate vicinity and import from sources more than 13 km away. We generally follow Geneste's seminal work (1985, 1988) distinguishing between local (0–5 km), regional (5–20 km) and supra-regional (>20 km) raw material sources. In the context of Early Ahmarian raw material economy at Al-Ansab 1, it is in most cases sufficient to separate local (0–5 km) and non-local (>5 km) raw materials.

<<Figure 7>>

Operational chain analysis

The here conducted technological analysis of lithic artifacts is inspired by classical *chaîne opératoire* methodology (Pelegrin et al. 1988; Sellet 1993; Soressi and Geneste 2011). It primarily focuses on the temporal structure of lithic operational sequences, although the spatial (or topological) relationships among artifacts within the reduction process and on the core reduction surface are also considered. All lithic artifacts > 0.5 cm were first laid out on tables and then pre-sorted according to their raw material attribution (see above). Within each group,

artifacts were sub-divided according to main artifact classes (cores, blanks of various configuration, core trimming elements [CTE], and tools) and further organized according to cortex cover and size. The presence and nature of non-cortical, natural surfaces and cleavages were also taken into consideration in this process.

Within each of the resulting sub-groups, the aim was to understand the interrelationships between artifacts, especially the spatial and technical links between blanks and the role of preparation and maintenance products. These observations were then compared between artifact types and the different raw material groups to reconstruct raw material-specific operational chains. All qualitative observations were noted in a database, and the composition of artifact groups was recorded. The presorting and technological analysis thereby benefited from the prior description and analysis of lithic attributes (Schyle 2015a, c; cf. Parow-Souchon 2020) and the general reconstruction of core reduction principles and concepts (Hussain 2015). Lithic refits, small in number but very instructive (Parow-Souchon 2020), were used to additionally calibrate and guide the technological interpretation. Dimensional data was obtained by measuring individual artifacts in knapping direction (technological orientation), recording the largest extension in mm; weights were recorded in decigrams.

Based on these premises and following established procedures of operational chain analysis (Tostevin 2012; Wenban-Smith et al. 2017: 347–367), we conducted a detailed reconstruction of reduction processes comparing the relationship and composition of eight reduction stages or steps within each of the documented outcrop-level raw material groups (cf. Parow-Souchon 2020: 22ff): Raw material acquisition/selection (Stage I), Initial Opening (Stage II), Decortification (Stage III), Preparation (Stage IV), Reduction/Primary production (Stage V), Maintenance (Stage VI), Discard (Stage VII) and Use (Stage VIII). These stages merely serve as an analytical grid to sort and compare dynamic lithic reduction trajectories and to examine inter-artifact relationships, they do not imply that technological processes are static or follow a technical straight-jacket – to the contrary.

Stage I (Raw material acquisition/selection) encompasses all unmodified exogenous nodules. Tested nodules bearing a maximum of three scars and those showing initial preparation traces are also sorted into this category. Stage II (Initial Opening) comprises completely cortical blanks or blanks with near-complete cortex cover and only a few anthropogenic scars. Cortex is the natural surface of the flint nodule in these cases – either limestone or chalk when the nodule has been procured from a primary outcrop. In case of a secondary context, the cortex is characterized by patinated or rolled/battered surfaces. Stage III (Decortification) includes pieces with more than 50 % cortex cover, also to facilitate extra-site comparison as the ‘>50 %’ category is frequently found in the literature (e.g. Coinman 1997: 113) and commonly identified with ‘primary elements’ – a category which was also used in previous work to classify and analyze the lithic material from the Wadi Sabra (Schyle 2015c).

Stage IV (Preparation) and Stage VI (Maintenance) can sometimes be difficult to separate. Differentiation is often possible only after reconstruction and understanding of the working principles of the encountered lithic system(s). Preparation includes primary core tablets, initial crested blades, and partially modified as well as partially-cortical crested blades. Lithic products showing laminar parallel scars indicative of previous extractions are sorted into the maintenance category. Maintenance products can clearly be correlated with the morphology of preserved cores in terms of their shape, curvature and the extent of twisting. They help determine the conceptual logic and sequentiality of core preparation and exploitation (cf. Fig. 8). Preserved hinges and/or other knapping accidents sometimes indicate why the technical operations associated with them became necessary and at what point in the laminar reduction process. Other preparation products are less strictly defined, and it is often more difficult to envision their former location on the core’s surface. An important class of maintenance products are convexity correction blades characterized by bulged or slightly twisted profiles where dorsal convexities diverge markedly from preserved ventral concavities. These products are often intercalated with the primary production of target central blanks (see below).

Stage V (Reduction/Primary production) includes the laminar target products of the operational chain, which are the logical result and central product of the standardized and well-defined core set-up. Additionally, the reduction stage comprises laminar reduction ‘byproducts’ – blanks that occur during primary blank production and typically derive from the lateral parts of the reduction surface or represent failed target products. Their main defining criterion is the absence of preparation or other maintenance traces and regular dorsal scars, and they are less regular in outline, axiality and profile than target central blanks.

Stage VI (Maintenance) includes well-defined core trimming elements (CTEs) with clear traces of organized, goal-oriented correction of knapping variables. Included in this category are secondary or tertiary core tablets, neocresting blades and lateral core rejuvenation flakes but also hinge corrections and overshots, most of which can be interpreted as deliberate and thus technical products in the larger context of Early Ahmarian reduction technologies. The surface-convexity maintenance products mentioned before, and which in reality span a continuum with strictly internal, primary products, are part of the maintenance stage as well.

Stage VII (Discard) is represented by cores from all reduction stages and core fragments that were abandoned on site. Stage VIII (Use) comprises all lithic tools, all pieces with macroscopically recognizable use-wear, as well as resharpening or recycling byproducts such as burin spalls.

<<Figure 8 >>

Curation analysis

Tool curation in the lithic material from Al-Ansab 1 was assessed in a qualitative and a quantitative manner. First, tools were sorted into broader modification types (e.g. laterally modified, ventrally retouched, truncation, endscraper, burin etc.). Next, the modification strategy was examined, generally distinguishing between ‘shaped’, ‘edge-modified’ and ‘unmodified’ tools. The aim here was to examine the relationship between tool morphotypes,

the overall composition of the toolkit, and different modes of manufacturing, using and maintaining the lithic tools in question. This qualitative approach pays special attention to the link between blank production and tool technology (see above), and seeks to identify differences in tool design and retouch intentionality, i.e. ‘final’ vs. transitional/‘transient’ tool forms (cf. Weißmüller 1995, 2003; Uthmeier 2004; see above).

The examination of transformation dynamics in lithic tools is based on a previous study of tool curation in the material from the Wadi Sabra (Parow-Souchon 2020: Appendix 1a3). It combines the above-mentioned qualitative approach with an assessment of lost blank volume during resharpening events. This conducted curational analysis separates lithic tools with a singular use phase, such as pieces interpreted as armature or projectile points, ‘ad hoc’ tools and unmodified pieces bearing use-wear from lithic tools with multiple phases of use such as edge-modified tools subjected to re-sharpening including other transient tools. Transient tool forms with multiple resharpening events are further evaluated in terms of their reduction intensity. The multiplication of working-ends on particular tools, for instance reflected in the fabrication of double endscrapers, multiple burins or various combination tools, is considered indicative of strategies aiming to extend tool biographies and thus promote tool curation.

In the case of endscrapers and laterally retouched implements, the loss of blank volume was also assessed quantitatively (cf. Kuhn 1990, Blades 2003, Kuhn 2004). Endscraper curation and reduction, especially for endscrapers on laminar blanks, is widely debated (e.g. Blades 2003; Kuhn 2004). Various proxies and measurements have been suggested to quantify the linear loss of volume due to tool-use, depletion and resharpening. Several methods (Barton 1988; Kuhn 1990; Hiscock and Clarkson 2005; Shott and Seaman 2015) were initially tested on a different Upper Palaeolithic assemblage from the Wadi Sabra with a larger endscraper sample and compared to the results from Al-Ansab 1 (Parow-Souchon 2020, Appendix 1a3). The derived endscraper reduction measures were compared statistically using Spearman’s r_S correlation. These investigations resulted in a simplified procedure that is used here.

The index of endscraper curation (termed $I_s(\frac{L}{Th})$) is calculated following Shott and Seeman (2015), using the formula:

$$I_s\left(\frac{Length}{Thickness}\right) = \frac{\left(x - \left(\frac{Length}{Thickness}\right)\right)}{y}$$

Where $x = Q98\left(\frac{Length}{Thickness}\right)_{allblanks}$ and $y = \max\left(x - \left(\frac{Length}{Thickness}\right)\right)$;

x therefore applies to the 98 % quartile for the length/thickness ratio of the endscrapers in the sample to exclude the largest blanks, and y is dependent on x .

In addition to this specialized reduction measure, the distal shape and form of endscrapers were qualitatively evaluated and described, paying special attention to the slight inward bend of the tool blank shortly before fracture termination. If this inward bend of the blank is well-recognizable, the endscraper has experienced little reductive treatment and is thus interpreted to record limited reshaping. If, by contrast, the distal part of the endscraper is flat and straight, an invasive treatment and comparatively large loss of mass is inferred.

Finally, the curational stage of the laterally-retouched elements was assessed via the widely employed Geometric Index of Reduction (GIR; Kuhn 1990). Briefly summarized, GIR compares the thickness of lithic blanks at the area of most retouch to the maximum thickness of the blank. A value of 1 indicates that retouch has reached the maximum thickness of the blank and is thus taken to indicate elevated levels of curation (cf. Kuhn 1990 and discussion of the flat flake problem in Dibble 1995; Hiscock and Clarkson 2005; and Parow-Souchon 2020). All statistical tests of metric attributes are conducted with the Mann-Whitney test and calculated in R, version 3.3.0 (R Core Team 2014, function: `wilcox.test`).

RESULTS

Raw material economy

The main raw material processed at Al-Ansab 1 is the grey, coarse-grained FRMG 9 found in the URC layers in the site's immediate vicinity, attesting to a clear focus on local raw material acquisition and reduction (Table 2; see method section for the definition of local). In total, 14.4 kg of lithic raw material was processed in the sampled area of 6.5 m², a mean of 2.2 kg per square meter (Table 2). 12.2 kg of those raw materials were collected from a distance of less than 500 m from the site, 10.2 kg from less than 40 m away and only 0.6 kg were brought to the site from sources outside of the Wadi Sabra – i.e. from a minimum distance of 13.5–18 km. More than 70 % of the total raw material mass was thus procured and directly on site (Table 2). The heavily-fractured AHP layers closeby (cf. Delage et al. 2020; see above) were exploited less often, comprising less than 15 % of the exploited raw material volume and less than 10 % of total raw material weight. Materials strictly exogeneous to the Al-Ansab locality, such as FRMG 3p, 4 and 7, were used only sparingly (n<2 %, weight<5 %) and were procured from URC not found directly on the site but available in the highland belt to the north and east. This category of non-local raw material also comprises five pieces of undefinable origin.

Table 2. Al-Ansab 1. Frequency and weight of lithic artifacts in the sample per raw material type (FRMG) and raw material group.

	Number		Weight		Walking distance to the site
	n	%	w (g)	%	
URC Ansab	1322	53.61	10175.2	70.72	2 min
FRMG 1	2	0.08	5.1	0.04	40 m
FRMG 5a	9	0.36	56.8	0.39	
FRMG 5b	22	0.89	25.9	0.18	
FRMG 9	1289	52.27	10087.4	70.11	
Silicified Limestone	361	14.64	823.5	5.72	5 min
FRMG 10	361	14.64	823.5	5.72	500 m
AHP/ASL	323	13.10	1246.5	8.66	5 min
FRMG 3b	40	1.62	179.5	1.25	500 m
FRMG 3d/FRMG 11	283	11.48	1067	7.42	
URC-General	43	1.74	604.8	4.20	
FRMG 3p	40	1.62	571.1	3.97	12h/18 km
FRMG 4	3	0.12	33.7	0.23	8h/13.5 km
Unknown Source	5	0.20	1.7	0.01	
FRMG 7	5	0.20	1.7	0.01	?
Indeterminable	412	16.71	1535.65	10.67	

Total	2466	100.00	14387.35	100.00	
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Raw material extraction and transformation focuses on the procurement of thick and massive sections of tabular URC Ansab flint seams from the Al-Ansab outcrop (Table 3), exhibiting lateral cortex coverage and patinated frontal surfaces, often used as a natural core back. The bulbar extractive surface is typically not preserved on any of these cores as future reduction procedures overprint these surfaces. Large core blanks are commonly split lengthwise or crosswise, with the cortical part forming the future back or side/flank of the core. In many cases, only a single lateral surface was prepared, while the other surfaces were left cortical (Fig. 9). Other nodule types and morphological configurations are of less importance at the site: Roundish nodules were used only rarely, directly mirroring their relative scarcity at the nearby outcrop. Direct procurement of large flake blanks for the setup and initialization of cores was also only rarely undertaken, as was the import of rolled and fissured river pebbles. Raw material selection at Al-Ansab 1 was thus centered on specific nodules with a preferred shape and quality. Nearly no ad hoc or opportunistic collection of nodules is evident.

Table 3. Al-Ansab 1. Nodule type per raw material group.

Cores Al-Ansab 1	FULL NODULES (outcrop)		LARGE FLAKES (outcrop)		RIVER PEBBLES (opportunistic)		TABULAR SECTIONS (outcrop)		UNDETERMINABLE SOURCE		Total amount	Total amount %	Total weight	Total weight %
	n	w(g)	n	w(g)	n	w(g)	n	w(g)	n	w(g)				
URC Ansab	3	298.8	3	314.8	1	254.0	18	2875.9	8	751.0	33	67.3	4494.5	79.2
Silicified limestone									1	76.8	1	2.0	76.8	1.4
AHP	2	150.7					6	410.3	1	69.1	9	18.4	630.1	11.1
URC General									2	186.4	2	4.1	186.4	3.3
Unknown sources											0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Indeterminable							2	145.0	2	144.9	4	8.2	289.9	5.1
Sum	5	449.5	3	314.8	1	254.0	26	3431.2	14	1228.2	49	100.0	5677.7	100.0
%	10	7.9	6	5.5	2	4.5	53	60.4	29	21.6				

URC Ansab raw material (Table 4) exhibits the highest reduction intensities and thus musters the most reliable values for interpreting the assemblage-wide management of lithic raw materials. Silicified limestone lacks cores, some of which were recovered in adjacent excavation squares but are not included in the present analysis. AHP and URC-General are less numerous and document relaxed reduction intensities as for example reflected in fewer blanks per core and in the general length statistics (Table 5). Yet, interestingly, AHP blades are significantly shorter than URC blades ($p = 0.004$, $U = 2963$, $z = 2.87967$; Mann-Whitney U test conducted in R (R Core Team, 2014); function: `wilcox.test`). Blades made from URC-General are also significantly longer than URC Ansab blades ($p < 0.001$, $U = 331.5$, $z = -4.27236$; Mann-Whitney U test), either indicating the export of larger URC Ansab blades from the site or the more systematic reduction of local Al-Ansab raw materials. An alternative explanation is the coarser texture of URC-General, possibly discouraging systematic bladelet production.

Table 4. Al-Ansab 1. Blank counts per raw material group.

Blank counts	URC Ansab		URC-General		AHP		Silicified Limestone		Unknown source		Indeterminable		Total	
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%
Flakes	427	32.4	14	32.6	66	20.4	107	30.0	1	20.0	0	0.0	615	6.3
Blades	394	29.9	26	60.5	65	20.1	72	20.2	4	80.0	0	0.0	561	5.7
Bladelets	443	33.7	1	2.3	178	55.1	176	49.3	0	0.0	0	0.0	798	8.2
Blade(lets)	837	63.6	27	62.8	243	75.2	248	69.5	4	80.0	0	0.0	1359	13.9
Subtotal Debitage items	1264	96.0	41	95.3	309	95.7	355	99.4	5	100.0	59	0.8	2033	20.8
Chunks (not classified by RM)	16	1.2		0.0	5	1.5		0.0		0.0	318	4.1	339	3.5
Chips (not classified by RM)		0.0		0.0		0.0		0.0		0.0	6056	78.2	6056	61.9
Subtotal Debris	16	1.2	0	0.0	5	1.5	0	0.0	0	0.0	6374	82.3	6395	65.3
Cores	26	2.0	2	4.7	9	2.8	1	0.3	0	0.0	0	0.0	38	0.4
Cores on flakes	6	0.5	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	6	0.1
Carinated pieces	4	0.3	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	0.3	0	0.0	0	0.0	5	0.1
Subtotal Cores	36	2.7	2	4.7	9	2.8	2	0.6	0	0.0	0	0.0	49	0.5
Total	1316	100.0	43	100.0	323	100.0	357	100.0	5	100.0	7743	100.0	9787	100.0
Tools	39	3.0	3	7.0	6	1.9	2	0.6	0	0.0	12	0.2	62	0.6
CTEs	97	7.4	6	14.0	8	2.5	10	2.8	0	0.0	0	0.0	121	1.2
Ratios														
Tool:Core	0.9		0.7		1.5		1.0						0.8	0.8
CTE:Core	2.7		3.0		0.9		5.0						2.5	2.5
Blanks:Core	35.1		20.5		34.3		177.5						41.5	41.5

Table 5. Al-Ansab 1. Length statistics for flakes and blades per raw material group.

	URC Ansab			URC-General			AHP			Silicified Limestone		
	Flakes	Blades	Total	Flakes	Blades	Total	Flakes	Blades	Total	Flakes	Blades	Total
Minimum	11	10	10	18	46	18	16	12	12	14	11	11
Average	35.3	44.4	40.8	38.8	75.2	63.1	34.6	33.1	33.7	31.2	36.5	33.2
SD	18	20.8	20.8	23.9	14.6	24.8	16.6	11.2	13.2	11.1	15.6	13.1
Median	31	43	37	32	75	72	31.5	32	32	30.5	40	31.5
Maximum	117	95	117	86	96	96	81	55	81	66	71	71
Total	166	213	379	6	12	18	22	41	63	38	22	60

Tools were manufactured from all raw material groups, with a dominance of URC Ansab flint encompassing all tool classes discarded on the site (Table 6). AHP and URC-General document numerically more restricted tool production, with burins and truncations are being the only tool types representing the URC-General group. The presence of this non-local raw material indicates the transport of some finished domestic tools to the site and likely provides evidence of mobile personal gear. It should be noted that the absence of el-Wad points in URC-General might also be an effect of sample size and the limited spatial coverage of the

here-analyzed lithic assemblage. This being said, the manufacture and retooling of el-Wad points was clearly a central on-site activity at Al-Ansab 1.

Table 6. Al-Ansab 1. Tool type groups per raw material group (cf. Parow-Souchon 2020: Appendix 3a).

	URC Ansab	URC General	AHP	Silicified Limestone	Indeterminable	Total
Endscraper	5					5
Burins	5	2	1	1	1	10
Truncations	6	1			2	9
Retouched pieces	10		3	1	2	16
El-Wad points	9		1		2	12
Non geometric Microliths	1		1			2
Use-wear	3					3
Total	39	3	6	2	7	57

<<Figure 9>>

Lithic technology

The majority of the lithic artifacts from Al-Ansab 1 are the products of a single well-defined operational chain. This operational sequence is oriented towards the production of straight, elongated blades from narrow-fronted unidirectional blade cores, mainly designated as blanks for el-Wad points but also employed as unmodified cutting implements. Other tool types, especially domestic tools such as burins, endscrapers or varied laterally retouched elements, were preferentially fabricated on byproducts and maintenance blades occurring during the production process and at various stages of preparation and maintenance. In addition, three carinated burins (Fig. 10:2), as defined by Le Brun-Ricalens and Brou (2013), and a single carinated endscraper (Fig. 10:3) were recovered. A single carinated burin was also found among the eroded material collected from the surface belonging to the same technological context (Fig. 10:4, Fig. 5c). Only the principal operational sequence is discussed in the following, even though the carinated component, especially is anecdotal, and its conceptual and techno-economic status requires further investigation.

<<Figure 10>>

Generally speaking, Al-Ansab 1 yields evidence for complete operational sequences with regard to the main raw material groups (Fig. 11), demonstrating that all stages of raw material management – from raw material acquisition to tool discard were enacted on-site. Investment into core preparation and maintenance is highest for URC Ansab and URC-General, while primary reduction intensity seems slightly higher in the strictly local/on-site URC Ansab raw material. Both AHP/ASL and Silicified Limestone document a decrease in preparatory and maintenance representation and are mainly characterized by primary production products. This trend is continued for unknown sources, and thus most likely strictly non-local raw materials, which are exclusively represented by primary production blanks indicating that at least a part of these products were imported either as prepared cores or as blanks. Each stage of the idealized lithic operational sequence is presented and described separately below.

<<Figure 11>>

Phase I: Selection of raw materials

Large tabular sections from URC outcrops were utilized for all documented core types and include different core reduction stages (Fig. 12). Two of these cores represent the offsite raw material group FRMG 3p: A single platform narrow-fronted core and a heavily reduced narrow fronted core with two independent reduction surfaces exploited from the same striking surface (Fig. 13:1). For example, there are no core preforms – i.e. nodules that were prepared but never fully initialized – among non-URC Ansab raw material types. This pattern is consistent with distance-dependent attrition and reduction intensity and concurrently attests to the raw material affluence at Al-Ansab 1 where the onsite raw material was variously tested and extensively reduced. It should be noted that carinated burins and the single documented carinated endscraper seem to be confined to specific raw material groups.

<<Figure 12-13>>

The majority of cores and core preforms are made on tabular sections (Table 7). The highest diversity in core types is found among undeterminable nodule configurations, representing cores reduced to an advanced stage so that their original nodule shape is no longer discernible. Increasing variation in core volume exploitation towards the end of the use-life of cores is generally expected to result in a greater variety of encountered core types but this mainly reflects curation at the end of the operational sequence where knapping is adjusted to changing volumetric and shape properties in order to ensure terminal productivity.

Table 7. Al-Ansab 1. Core type by nodule type.

	Full nodules (outcrop)		Large flakes (outcrop)		Tabular sections (outcrop)		River pebbles (opportunistic)		Unknown source	
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%
Narrow-fronted	3	60	1	33.3	15	60	1	100	7	50
Bidirectional	1	20								
Double									1	7.1
Core on flake									1	7.1
Core fragment					1	4			1	7.1
Core pre-form			1	33.3	7	28				
Residual cores	1	20			2	8			1	7.1
Carinated burin			1	33.3					2	14.3
Carinated endscraper									1	7.1
Total	5	100	3	100	25	100	1	100	14	100.0

In summary, raw material selection in Al-Ansab 1 unequivocally centers on the acquisition of tabular sections from the local onsite outcrop for the production of well-defined and carefully set up single platform narrow-fronted cores. Several other options were available to knappers but played a subordinate role.

Phase II–IV: Initialization, decortication and preparation

The chosen nodules were opened on-site and apparently not tested directly at the outcrop before being imported to the site. Interestingly, however, initialization products are found only for URC Ansab and AHP/ASL, while decortification is well-attested for all major raw material groups but was most important also for URC Ansab and AHP/ASL raw materials (cf. Fig. 11).

This pattern suggests that AHP/ASL raw materials were at least partially imported as cortical nodules to the site, while URC-General and Silicified Limestone were more often imported in other formats (e.g. core preforms, initialized cores, blanks, tools).

Phase II-IV knapping procedures normally proceeded by establishing a single platform for initial preparation and decortification (see Fig. 14:1–3). Suitable natural platforms were often not further modified and opportunistically seized (see Fig. 15:2). Initial opening flakes are larger than primary products and blades are of average size when compared to the full sample of blanks (flakes $p < 0.0001$, U1121, $z = -4.27236$ /blades $p = 0.14156$, U 940, $z = 1.47161$; Mann-Whitney U test; Table 8). This seems to suggest that there is no strict technical distinction between cortical and non-cortical blades and/or that it was not a primary concern for Early Ahmarian knappers to decorticate the full length of future reduction surfaces.

<<Figure 14–15>>

Table 8. Al-Ansab 1. Length statistics for flakes and blades by operational stage.

	II - Initial opening		III - Decortification		IV - Preparation		V - Reduction	
	Flakes	Blades	Flakes	Blades	Flakes	Blades	Flakes	Blades
Minimum	13	21	11	15	24	29	11	10
Average	42.3	35.7	31.1	38.1	54.2	57.3	26.1	35.3
SD	19.8	12.7	10.8	16.0	17.8	17.5	9.2	16.4
Median	40	42	31	37	52	59	24	31,5
Maximum	81	44	58	64	85	81	58	86
Total	12	3	38	10	29	17	129	212
	VI - Maintenance		VIII -Use		Total		V - Reduction	
	Flakes	Blades	Flakes	Blades	Flakes	Blades	Target blades	Byproduct blades
Minimum	17	22	36	17	11	10	22	10
Average	42.7	61.2	67.3	37.8	34.2	42.6	42.7	33.3
SD	19.9	18.1	36.9	18.6	17.3	20.2	17.1	16.1
Median	38	62	58	31	30,5	39	37,5	30
Maximum	117	96	108	76	117	96	77	86
Total	48	79	3	16	264	338	24	174

Secondary flaking characteristics show a tendency towards more pronounced bulbs for products from early phases of the operational chain (II–IV), which is likely indicative of the use of a harder or directly applied hammer (see also Hussain 2015: Fig. VII-3). This is especially pronounced in Phase II (Parow-Souchon 2020: table 19) where a virtual absence of diffuse bulbs is noticeable. This pattern suggests a technical differentiation in terms of knapping techniques and gestures between core initialization and preparation on the one hand and primary blank production on the other, pointing to a well-defined technical infrastructure where different processes are linked to different reduction modalities. This finding is consistent with the results from other Early Ahmarian assemblages where a broad distinction between internal and edge-near reduction has similarly been suggested (see discussion).

Decortification generally alternates with preparatory procedures, and the distinction between the two relies on the technical character of preparatory products. Core preparation is primarily concerned with the establishment of a distal keel and functional lateral and longitudinal core convexities. Initial preparation produced very large (Fig. 16:1) and often, but not always, cortical flakes, especially when cores were roughly shaped to establish the desired narrow-fronted core architecture. These flakes are also significantly larger (Table 8) than those deriving from primary production ($p = 0.008$, $U1757.5$, $z -2.64535$, blades $p = 0.497$, $U 924$, $z -0.68267$; Mann-Whitney U test). Lateral and distal core convexities were subsequently established (see Fig. 16:2–3) by advancing at least halfway up to the back of the core (Fig. 17:2), often focusing on a single lateral side (Fig. 17:1).

<<Figure 16–17>>

Cresting of the distal keel, and in some cases the creation of a keel on the back of the core (see Fig. 18:1), is documented mainly unilaterally but was recurrently employed in order to construct a functional core architecture for primary blank production. Bilateral (see Fig. 19:2–4) or natural (see Fig. 14:4–5) crests were thereby used to open the reduction surface, and

the latter was apparently left mostly untouched until the preparation of lateral core surfaces and the installation of proper flanks was completed (see Fig. 17:2).

<<Figure 18–19>>

Towards the end of the preparatory stage, lateral cortical blades were removed from the outskirts of the primary central reduction surface. Overshots were sometimes used to further refine the distal convexity of the target reduction surfaces. Secondary core tablets were sometimes already detached during preparation stages, as for example indicated by extended lateral preparation operations with a concurring lack of frontal removals on such tablets (Fig. 19:5; cf. Fig. 8). Several cores from Al-Ansab 1 were seemingly discarded during this operational stage (Fig. 17–18), mainly due to discovered physical faults or crevices in their raw material. This observation generally supports the conclusion drawn earlier that URC Ansab material was often not tested at the outcrop but brought in pre-selected configurations to the site in order to be transformed into specific core forms.

Phase V: Reduction/primary production

The reduction or primary production phase targets straight and regular laminar blanks of various dimensions, especially central naturally-pointed blades which are almost symmetrical in their outline (Fig. 19:6–9). However, these central laminar products are not frequently encountered in the Al-Ansab 1 assemblage (Table 9), pointing to an extensive export of these target products (or sample bias/a combination of both) either as plain blanks or el-Wad points, the preferred tool class associated with this blank type (Hussain 2015; Richter et al. 2020; Parow-Souchon 2020). Bladelets certainly form a separate production goal at Ansab 1 (Hussain 2015; Gennai 2021), even though they are often obtained from advanced core reduction stages. Bladelets (laminar blanks < 12 mm wide) are generally more numerous than blades sensu stricto (Gennai 2021) and many of the encountered blades are maintenance products, but this may similarly be due to the large-scale exportation of central target blades. This being said, core preforms (cf.

e.g. Fig. 17) undoubtedly showcase the potential for early bladelet production and there is also evidence for other independent bladelet exploitation opportunities (see below).

Statistically, target blades and blades turned into tools are indistinguishable in length ($p=0.275$, U 152, z 1.09051; Mann-Whitney U test) and ‘byproduct’ blades are significantly smaller than central target products ($p=0.006$, U 1362, z -2.7569; Mann-Whitney U test; **Table 8**). These target blade(let)s are derived from the center of the reduction surface, while byproduct blades are of lateral origin (**Fig. 9**; cf. **Hussain 2015: Figs. VII-9, VII-10, VII-13 and VII-14**). More lateralized and twisted, off-axis products were removed to preserve the lateral convexity of cores and to restore the distal convergence of reduction surfaces and were initially termed technical blades/flakes by Hussain (2015: 137). These ‘technical’ blades are grouped into the maintenance category here to recognize their special role in preserving the lateral-distal curvature of the core during primary production (**Fig. 9**). It is also worth nothing that these products attest to an ‘embedded’ mode of maintenance (Hussain 2015), ensuring a continuous reduction stream and thus enhancing global laminar productivity. Byproducts, as defined above, generally form the largest blank category on site, bearing unilaterally regular, straight reduction negatives and on the other lateral side more irregular negatives from preparatory actions, and are often slightly twisted (**Fig. 19**:10, **20**:1–2, see the refitted lateral and central but not pointed blade in Fig. 20:3). Irregular, non-cortical flakes and tiny bladelets are also included in this category.

Table 9. Al-Ansab 1. Operational stages and diagnostic products per raw material group (OC: Operational Chain; OC Product in VIII – Use indicates the blank type supporting tool use).

OC Phase	OC Product	URC Ansab	AHP	SL	URC General	Unknown Sources	Intederminable	Total
II - Initial Opening	Fully cortical opening	29	5	0	0	0	7	41
III - Decortification		104	24	11	2	0	26	167

	Core tablet primary	6	2				1	9
	Large piece from early preparation	4		4	2			10
	Primary crest	3	1				1	5
	Secondary crest distal	1	1				1	3
	Lateral core preparation	42	6		1		1	50
	Lateral platform correction		1					1
	Overshot	1					1	2
	Initial burin spall carinated	5	1	1			3	10
IV Preparation		62	12	5	3	0	8	90

	Reduction target piece	80	41	16	5		22	164
	Reduction byproducts	741	188	288	17	5	256	1495
V - Reduction		821	229	304	22	5	278	1659

	Core tablet secondary	8		1			6	15
	Core tablet lateral				1			1
	Lateral core trimming	118	21	20	6		18	183
	Neocreting, distal rejuvenation	32	1	1	2		2	38
	Hinge correction	20	6	5			6	37
	Overshot	18	4	2			5	29
VI Maintenance		196	32	29	9	0	37	303

VII - Discard		32	9	2	2	0	4	49
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	Flake/blade	28	5	2	3		6	48
	Tool resharpening waste	2					1	3
	Burin spall	11					3	14
	Fully cortical opening		1					1
	Core Tablet primary	1						1
	Primary crest	1						1
	Lateral core preparation	0						1
	Reduction waste	1						1
	Secondary core tablet	2						2
	Secondary crest	1						1
	Back maintenance						1	1
	Lateral core trimming	2						2
	Plain Blank with use-wear	3						3
VIII - Use		52	6	2	3	0	11	79

Indeterminable	Indeterminable	20	5	1	2	0	40	68
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<<Figure 20>>

Laminar products from Phase V are further characterized by weakly developed bulbs and lips are frequently present, while dorsal scars are generally rare (Parow-Souchon 2020:

table 19, 22 and 23). This lends support to the interpretation of edge-near (non-internal) percussion with acute knapping angles during primary production (Hussain 2015). Abrasion is often used to prepare the platform's edge for a new series of laminar removals (Fig. 21). The lack of *esquiellements du bulbe*, or shattered bulbs, argues against the utilization of a soft stone hammer (*Pierre tendre*; cf. Floss and Weber 2013; Pelegrin 2000) and, coupled with the overall scarcity of hertzian cones, strongly points to a predominant utilization of organic percussion instruments. Direct impact, resulting in platforms of >2 mm depth (cf. Soriano et al. 2007: 690), can only be observed during core initialization and preparation, again supporting the separation between more internal, direct knapping during early reduction stages and peripheral knapping during later stages. AHP raw materials notably deviate from this general flaking pattern (cf. Parow-Souchon 2020: table 19). This raw material type seemingly exhibits no internal segmentation in terms of knapping technique and blank attributes are consistent with indirect, tangential percussion throughout all operational stages. The fact that raw material properties, reduction technology and knapping mode are co-adapted in URC Ansab, even though the latter is a strictly local raw material, shows that the encountered in-situ reduction technology is planned and reflects technological curation and economization.

<<Figure 21>>

Phase VI–VII: Maintenance and discard

Maintenance yields the second largest group of products after the primary reduction phase where the bulk of target products is obtained. Reduction and maintenance alternate during blank production and are frequently intertwined rather than forming discrete stages. The separation between the two is reflective of the corrective character of the maintenance products described above and maintenance is often 'embedded'. Most maintenance products at Al-Ansab 1 result from lateral correction procedures, either in the form of technical blades (Fig. 20:4–8) or fully-lateralized corrective blanks – both flakes and blades – bearing none or only a few negatives of

foregoing preparatory processes or, alternatively, a portion or remnant of past reduction surfaces (Fig. 20:9–10, 22:1–3).

<<Figure 22–23>>

Knapping or raw material errors were only in extreme cases corrected from the back of the core. A single core fragment (Fig. 22:4) possibly represents a knapping accident occurring during the maintenance process, as indicated by terminated (incomplete) reduction scars and the presence of a large part of the former reduction surface. When lateral correction by technical blades proved insufficient, distal crests were applied, and plunging neocresting (Fig. 23:1–3; cf. Lengyel 2007) was employed rather invasively to readjust the disto-lateral part of the core. These mainly unilateral crests served to guide the extraction of a large plunging blade, removing a large chunky piece from the distal end of the core without altering the configuration of the proximal part of the reduction surface. These blades constitute the second largest group of maintenance products at Al-Ansab 1. Hinge fractures emerging during the reduction process were also corrected by means of thick maintenance blades or flakes (Fig. 24:6–7). Uncrested overshot products were used to correct or rejuvenate the distal-lateral curvature of exploited cores in less severe cases.

<<Figure 23–24>>

Platform maintenance is relatively simple and thick core tablets were detached proximally directly from the reduction surface or, more rarely, from adjacent lateral core surfaces (Fig. 24:1–5). These core tablets bear evidence for hard hammer percussion such as pronounced impact scars and evident hertzian cones (Fig. 24:4), sometimes even clear plunging traces (Fig. 24:1). On the respective core tablets, the extent of lateral preparation is easily discernible, again indicating that lateral shaping of the core was a graded process and generally intertwined with the main blank reduction process.

Discard of the cores, finally, is rarely the result of overexploitation and often has to do with difficult-to-correct knapping errors or flaws and fissures in the raw material matrix. This

pattern is consistent with the raw material affluence at Al-Ansab 1 but is certainly complicated by the pronounced variability of core types encountered especially in advanced reduction stages (see above). The emerging picture is thus in general accordance with a balanced compromise between raw material economization and overavailability. The one truly bidirectional core encountered in the sample (cf. Fig. 10: 1) is most likely also made on a raw material variant that has traveled considerable distances to reach Al-Ansab. This core exhibits a markedly flattened, and thus almost exhausted, longitudinal reduction surface convexity and was probably co-opted as a bladelet core at the end of its use-life.

Phase VIII: Use

The tool assemblage from Al-Ansab 1 yields a typical Early Ahmarian signature, consisting mainly of el-Wad points, endscrapers, burins, truncations and laterally retouched pieces (Table 10; Fig. 25; cf. Schyle 2015b). Endscrapers are more numerous than burins and most tools have a single working-end. There is only one double endscraper in the assemblage with two separate working edges. Other multitools are burin types with clear modification sequences. The toolkit is generally dominated by edge-near modifications and retouch is rarely transformative, i.e. substantially alters the inherited blank morphology, pointing to an important relationship between blank selection and tool production (cf. Hussain 2015; Richter et al. 2020). Abundant laterally retouched pieces complete the picture of tool forms primarily devised for specific activities but reduced half-live periods and limited frequency of use.

Table 10. Al-Ansab 1. Tools per raw material group (Type list cf. Parow-Souchon 2020: Appendix 3a).

		URC			URC		
		Ansab	AHP	SL	General	Indeterminable	Total
A	Endscraper	5	0	0	0	0	5
A01	Single end-scraper	4					4
A03	Double flat end-scraper	1					1
B	Burins	5	1	1	2	1	10

B01	Straight dihedral burin	2					2
B02	Offset dihedral burin	1	1		1		3
B05	Multiple dihedral burin				1	1	2
B12	Burin on a convex truncation	1					1
B87	Burin on previous facet	1		1			2
E	Truncations	6	0	0	1	2	9
E01	Truncated flake	2					2
E02	Truncated blade	1			1	1	3
E03	Piece with curved truncation	1					1
E05	Backed and truncated piece					1	1
E99	Oblique Truncation	2					2
H	Retouched pieces	10	3	1	0	2	18
H81	Fragment of retouched blade	3	1			1	5
H82	Partially retouched flake	5	2	1		1	9
H83	Partially retouched blade	1					1
H88	Retouched flake	1					1
I	Special tools	9	1	0	0	2	12
I01	El-Wad point	9	1			2	12
J	Non-geometric microlith	1	1	0	0	0	2
J01	Pointed bladelet with fine retouch	1	1				2
X1	Use-wear	3					3
	Subtotal Ahmarian tools	39	6	2	3	7	57
	Tools not included in previous tables	16	4	3	1	2	26
A13	Carinated end-scraper			1			1
B07	Carinated burin	3					3
J10	Bladelet with inverse retouch	3	1	1			5
H06	Piece with inverse or alternate retouch	1					1
H94	Retouched blade, inverse	1					1
(X2)	Trowel retouch)	(8)	(3)	(1)	(1)	(2)	(15)
Total		47 (55)	7 (10)	4 (5)	3 (4)	7 (9)	68 (83)

El-Wad points occupy a special place in the assemblage. Together with inversely retouched bladelets they also represent tools with a singular use phase which are usually produced onsite but for the clear purpose of off-site utilization, presumably as hunting gear including projectile points and versatile butchery knives. 12 el-Wad points (cf. Fig. 25:1–2) are recorded in the Al-Ansab 1 sample. Three are intact and were seemingly discarded or lost in an unused state, while the rest are point fragments, mostly distal parts of former el-Wad points. The presence of both complete and broken el-Wad points attests to in-situ manufacturing of lithic points and retooling activities at the site.

<<Figure 25>>

Weakly transitional tool types, mainly burins and truncations are present at Al-Ansab 1 in comparatively low numbers (cf. Table 10). Endscrapers are underrepresented in comparison to burins or truncations, and only four specimens proved suitable for quantitative reduction/curation analysis. These four endscrapers yielded elevated $I_s(\frac{L}{Th})$ values (Table 11). The less reduced specimens are made on complete blanks, while the two apparently heavy-reduced endscrapper modifications are associated with broken blanks.

Table 11. Al-Ansab 1. Resharpener intensity values for single endscrapers (RD=Retouch direction; L= Length; W=Width; Th=Thickness; GIR=Geometric Index of Reduction, for an explanation of t and T, refer to Kuhn 1990).

Figure No.	25:6	25:7	25:8	-
L (retouch direction [RD])	27.89	79.77	60.15	38.99
W (RD)	18.66	19.7	44.9	50.46
Th (RD)	7.93	10.96	10.64	11.74
Blank complete	no	yes	yes	no
Is (L/Th)	0.99	0,73	0,84	1
GIR (t/T)	1.01	0.93	0.74	0.93
Distal end preserved?	no	yes	yes	yes

Technologically, the four analyzed endscrapers belong to two groups: Wider specimens on flakes and narrower, slender specimens on blades. The implied width difference might suggest hafting to handles of different sizes and thus divergent endscrapper use and function but this hypothesis needs to be corroborated by use-wear analysis. The blade-based endscrapers closely resemble each other morphologically (Fig. 25:6). The documented breakage pattern is probably a result of pressure from the ventral side, suggesting fragmentation during use. The lacking slight ventral bend on the distal ends of most complete endscrapper blanks suggests multiple resharpening events prior to discard. The intact endscrapper shown in Fig. 25:7 is made on a thick and long blade and exhibits a slight inward curvature at its distal end. A retouch

accident resulted in a protruding hinge on the retouched part forming the endscraper's working-end. Two attempts to remove the protrusion from the ventral side of the blank are discernible, yet they were unsuccessful and only added to the existing hinge. After these correction attempts failed, at least five additional removals are documented at the dorsal ridge above the hinge in a final attempt to remove the hinge and reactivate the endscraper. A number of successive impact points is additionally documented on the distal end of the dorsal side of the blade blank, all of which did not succeed in restoring the tool's core functionality. The blank was still 8 cm long at the time of discard and was thus probably abandoned prematurely, as also indicated by its comparatively low $I_s(\frac{L}{Th})$ value.

GIR values on lateral modifications (Table 12) vary widely but the values do not increase continuously, potentially hinting at discrete resharpening events. Only four tools in the assemblage were curated by means of adding another functional edge: The double endscraper mentioned above, two multiple dihedral burins (Fig. 25:9) and one burin on convex truncation. Surprisingly, the double endscraper was abandoned on site and not exported, even though its raw material body still offered plenty of reduction potential.

Notably, endscrapers represent a strictly local class of tools, and there are no documented endscrapers made of non-local raw materials at Al-Ansab 1. Endscrapers were thus possibly not part of the mobile toolkit or 'personal gear' (Binford 1977), which mainly comprised finished el-Wad points and plain blades as well as burins and truncations on blades (Fig. 25:10) as indicated by the import evidence of AHP and URC-General tools (see above). This pattern, although admittedly grounded in small numbers, may elucidate a distinct economic strategy of tool design, use and transport in the Early Ahmarian of Al-Ansab 1. Endscrapers seem to be truly domestic tool types with reduced mobility, and they can be grouped into a larger class of stationary tool including the *prima facie* expedient transformation of CTEs such as core tablets and other large production byproducts into larger scrapers and burins. These tools were sometimes curated but they were produced mainly for onsite use. Mobile gear, by

contrast, consisted of prepared cores and cortical core preforms (see above), central blade blanks and laminar tools including el-Wad points. The tool component within this mobile suite of materials was apparently highly specialized and not intended for extensive reuse.

Table 12. Al-Ansab 1. GIR values for lateral modifications (FRMG = Flint raw material group; type list cf. Parow-Souchon 2020: Appendix 3a).

RM	Tool Type	GIR
FRGM 9	H82	0.20
FRGM 3d	J01	0.22
FRGM 9	H82	0.38
FRGM 9	H83	0.38
Indeterminable	H81	0.54
FRGM 9	J01	0.57
FRGM 3d	H82	0.60
FRGM 10	H82	0.71
FRGM 9	H81	0.72

DISCUSSION

Techno-economy and mobility at Al-Ansab 1

The lithic technology of Al-Ansab 1 is well-defined and homogeneous, and thus testifies to a standardized and planned organization of technological processes. Lithic techno-economy at Al-Ansab 1 is governed by a fully integrated production system, furnishing a range of laminar blanks with different technical and morphological characteristics as well as a diverse spectrum of flake blanks of various configurations. Blanks are generally differentiated according to their position in the operational sequence, their precise location of detachment on the exploitation surface, and the employed knapping mode (cf. Hussain 2015; Richter et al. 2020). Internal axial production on the main exploitation surface delivers slim, relatively straight, and convergent blade blanks, with some potential for the intercalated, opportunistic production of varied bladelet forms as also proposed for Umm el Tlel (Ploux and Soriano 2003). These central products are preferentially used to manufacture el-Wad points or utilized as plain cutting-edges (Hussain 2015; Parow-Souchon 2020). The techno-morphological characteristics of the

produced blanks gradually change with their degree of lateralization on the principal exploitation surface. Fully lateral blanks, often twisted and distally bulged, are sometimes selected for other domestic tools such as endscrapers, burins, or non-formal tools (Hussain 2015). Maintenance and preparatory products yield the bulk of non-mobile, domestic tools and especially thick correction blades and CTEs are used as blanks for these tools.

This organization of knapping stands in contrast to fully-serial lithic production strategies of the developed Upper Palaeolithic seems more consistent with an evolved 'assortment' character of blank production (ger. *Sortiment*; sensu Richter 1997: 253f.), mirrored in the selection and utilization of a wide range of internally differentiated blanks spanning preparatory and primary production stages within a single operational sequence. The morpho-technical qualities of their maintenance and preparation products differ from their counterparts of internal primary production and supply the basic stock of blanks for bulky heavy-duty tools (Hussain 2015; Parow-Souchon 2020; Richter et al. 2020). Core flank flakes or initialization products are in turn often transformed into semicircular endscrapers or other informal tools, and core tablets frequently serve as burin matrices (Hussain 2015; Parow-Souchon 2020). This pattern is consistent with other other Early Ahmarian assemblages in the Southern Levant (cf. Davidzon and Goring-Morris 2003; Goring-Morris and Davidzon 2006) and suggests that the internal diversification of blanks in terms of size and morphology powers toolkit diversification. From this perspective, Early Ahmarian blank production is not rooted in the idea of a 'universal blank'.

This integrated yet diversified production system concurrently yields evidence for some weak internal 'ramification' (sensu Bourguignon et al. 2004; Ducasse 2010) since both, the stratified assemblage and the surface collection from Al-Ansab 1, document lateral correction flakes and other narrow-edged products with secondary bladelet removals. Based on her analysis of the Early Ahmarian lithic assemblage from Boker A, Monigal (2003) has argued that each cycle of primary blade production is only moderate in productivity. The production

process is regularly interrupted by invasive preparatory procedures when embedded corrective measures are not sufficient anymore. Each preparatory intervention enables a new cycle of blade production with only a handful of target central products at best. The reconstructed operational sequence of the Early Ahmarian at Al-Ansab 1 supports this interpretation; it illustrates an original compromise between the quasi-serial production of convergent blades characteristic of Upper Paleolithic technocomplexes across Eurasia (see e.g. recent summary of Western Europe by Pelegrin 2011) and the diversified and weakly ramified assortment production indicative of many Middle Paleolithic technologies (cf. Boëda 1995; Richter 1997; cf. Hussain 2013: 190f., 2015).

The lithic technology from Al-Ansab 1 conforms to a blank production economy (*économie du débitage*) rather than a raw material economy (*économie de la matière première*) or an economy purely driven by tool production imperatives (cf. Perlès 1980, 1991; Pigeot 1987; Boëda 2013). The primary locus of blank diversification, anticipating the structure of the toolkit and possible future cutting-edge requirements, is the organization of volumetric exploitation and the resulting chronological segmentation of operational sequences in terms of obtained products and byproducts. This techno-economic principle is also illustrated by the trade-offs between blank production, blank selection, and tool production. The structure of the available blank pool – itself a result of the synergistic interplay of core configuration and knapping modalities – guides both blank selection and tool manufacture (cf. Davidzon and Goring-Morris 2003; Monigal 2003; Becker 2003; Goring-Morris and Davidzon 2006; Hussain 2015, Parow-Souchon 2020), and there is therefore a well-developed structural coherence between all of these operational stages, so that the inheritances of each stage shape selection and reduction in the subsequent operational stage.

Tool production does not introduce new imperatives or norms but instead follows, exploits and to some extent reinforces the achievements of earlier stages of the operational sequence, most notably blank production. Tool modifications does not substantially interfere

with the inherited shapes and traits of the produced blanks but rather correct, accentuate or consolidate these traits. Retouch intentionalities therefore co-vary with more-or-less subtle differences in blank origin and morphology. This is also reflected in the often-marginal character of retouch and the generally low extent of assemblage-level modification (cf. Parow-Souchon 2020), including mounting evidence that plain regular blanks constituted an important production goal as well and were probably exported in significant numbers from Early Ahmarian sites. Generally speaking, the emphasis on preparation and blank normalization at the expense of substantial modification investment might suggest that adequate cutting-edge configurations could easily be achieved without modification. Similar observations have been made in Nahal Nizanna XIII, where large parts of the Early Ahmarian assemblage could be refitted (Davidzon and Goring-Morris 2003).

The detailed raw material analysis presented in this study further demonstrates that raw material economies at Al-Ansab 1 were highly conventionalized and predominantly targeted high-quality, local raw materials of particular shapes and sizes. Only a few cores were imported to the site as their exploitation indicates reduction strategies connected to extending their use-life and distal productivity. In principal, however, Early Ahmarian knappers targeted mainly tabular sections of the locally outcropping raw material, facilitating the preparation and setup of protuberant, narrow-fronted cores with a high keel. Selection of raw materials is thus highly targeted and not expedient even though high-quality raw material is overabundant. Local URC raw material is additionally well-represented by products of all operational stages, indicating the complete transformation and consumption of raw materials at the site.

Combined with the results of the curational analysis and the qualitative characteristics of the lithic toolkit with a clear focus on edge-modified, final tools with only a few, weakly transient forms, the techno-economic profile of Al-Ansab 1 highlights the complexities of Early Ahmarian adaptation and mobility. The expedient quality of the toolkit with an important role of unmodified regular blades contrasts the curated nature of the blank production process. The

cardinal problem of cutting-edge supply is solved not by means of adopting diversified strategies of raw material management and lithic reduction, but instead by the internal organization of knapping itself, yielding well-differentiated spectra of blanks that support blank-tool coherence and the segregation between less and more mobile blank and tool forms. Flakes, endscrapers and domestic tools on cortical pieces and CTEs as well as expedient laterally retouched pieces anchor the stationary toolkit, while central blades, el-Wad tools and other specialized blade tools supply the mobile toolkit. The latter provides evidence for provisioning of individuals (Kuhn 1995, 2021) while the former is consistent with activity provisioning (Kuhn 2004). Raw material acquisition patterns, by contrast, take up a middle ground between curated and expedient even though the picture is probably somewhat skewed due to the marked raw material affluence at the Al-Ansab locality. That said, raw material economy is fairly monospecific with a overwhelming focus on high-quality URC raw materials of local origin. The Early Ahmarian lithic production technology of Al-Ansab 1 takes advantage of preselected nodule shapes and configurations, and ramification as well as separate bladelet production is almost exclusively documented for the same raw materials.

The Al-Ansab 1 evidence points to an integrated strategy in which landscape patches of abundant high-quality lithic raw material played an integral role in shaping human mobility and lithic reduction. The scheduled visit of productive outcrops is paired with an integrated blank production scheme where all tool requirements can be satisfied on a single core matrix. Although some core preforms and cortical nodules were most likely imported, strategic planning does therefore not centre primarily on place provisioning (Kuhn 1995) but signals an original combination of individual and activity provisioning. While lithic reduction technology as a whole is mostly stationary, the few imported non-local cores can be interpreted as mobile safety-nets when facing unanticipated blank shortages or other situations where quick on-spot cutting-edge replenishment was required. Integrated, assortment-like Early Ahmarian core technologies are not only well adapted to high-quality raw materials – and in turn depend on

rich and dependable raw material sources – but can support diverse tool needs within one core reduction cycle. As Monigal (2003) has pointed out at Boker A, Early Ahmarian cores are thus ideal all-purpose blank reservoirs but their weight probably inhibited systematic, large-scale transportation across the landscape, especially in a high-mobility environment.

In total, then, the predictability, affluence and quality of the URC raw material outcrop at Al-Ansab seems to have been an integral component of planned Early Ahmarian movement in the Southern Levant. Paired with a generally diverse toolkit and a broad spectrum of represented activities including possibly hearths, shallow pits and faunal evidence for gazelle hunting on the one hand and clustered activity zones that were apparently rapidly buried on the other hand, Al-Ansab 1 is best interpreted as representing repeated but short-term earlier Upper Palaeolithic occupations (Richter et al. 2020; Parow-Souchon 2020; Schoenenberg 2018; Sauer and Schoenenberg 2021). Sauer and Schoenberg (2021) have shown that the location of the site at the edge of the Jordanian escarpment fits into a larger pattern of strategic site choice close to specialized and often humid locations of high ungulate availability. The URC Ansab raw material source was certainly an important locational factor but prey accessibility was thus another key criterium for site selection. The techno-economic data presented here is not only consistent with this scenario, but further suggests that lithic technology in the Early Ahmarian is an effective adaptation to a highly mobile lifestyle in the shadow of ungulate prey, especially gazelle – a picture that is in good accord with previous landscape archaeological syntheses by Gladfelter (1997: 370) and Williams (2000, 2003) which have similarly highlighted the significance of a variety of key resources including water, raw material patches and mobile prey species for Early Ahmarian settlement systems.

The combined archaeological evidence from Al-Ansab 1 therefore adds to the growing body of knowledge picturing landuse and mobility in the Early Ahmarian of the Southern Levant as highly residential in nature (Parow-Souchon 2020, Richter et al. 2020). Provisioning strategies centred on individuals and key activities in the landscape resulting in similar sites

with relatively short-term occupations, high dislocational frequencies and moderate-to-low mobility distances. In the Early Ahmarian, residentiality seems connected to unusually spurious occupations within a generally large contextual area spanning large parts of the marginal zone.

The place of Al-Ansab 1 in the Early Ahmarian

In accordance with previous investigations of Al-Ansab 1 (Schyle 2015a; Hussain 2015; Hauck 2015; Parow-Souchon 2020, Richter et al. 2020), the here presented technological and techno-economic evidence places the site's lithic assemblage into the southern variant of the larger Early Ahmarian techno-complex – the 'Southern Ahmarian' (see Kadowaki et al. 2015). Albeit detailed cross-site comparisons are still lacking, the Southern Ahmarian is currently defined by the prevalence of unidirectional core concepts with elements of embedded preparation. This is reflected in the exploitation of standardized narrow-fronted blade cores to derive regular, thin, and pointed/convergent blanks for the production of el-Wad points, marginally retouched blades and bladelets as well as a suite of domestic tools (Bar-Yosef and Belfer 1977; Davidzon and Goring-Morris 2003; Monigal 2003; Ploux and Soriano 2003; Goring-Morris and Davidzon 2006; Bar-Yosef and Belfer-Cohen 2010; Hussain 2015). Core reduction revolves around hyper-acute platform angles ($< 70^\circ$), involves abrasion and platform normalization and entails a division between preparatory stages (internal percussion) and primary blank production (tangential/edge-near percussion; cf. Monigal 2003; Goring-Morris and Davidzon 2006). By contrast, the Northern Ahmarian – mainly found along the coastal strip and the Levantine woodland biome – comprises more varied core exploitation approaches, including convergent and bidirectional exploitation schemes, and registers a range of wide and comparatively thick laminar products (cf. Ronen and Vandermeersch 1972; Azoury 1986; Kuhn et al. 2009; Williams and Bergman 2010; Tostevin 2012; Kadowaki et al. 2015; Abulafia et al. 2021). The Northern Ahmarian is distinguished by a 'robust' point technology including el-Wad points and so-called Ksar 'Akil and Abu Halka points with sometimes invasive retouch (Bergman 1981,

1987; Kuhn et al. 2009). The toolkit encompasses backed elements, special tool types, such as *pointes à face plane* and so-called *chamfreins*, and endscrapers are usually more numerous than burins (Newcomer 1968/69; Bergman and Newcomer 1983; Kuhn et al. 2009). The distinct nature of Northern Ahmarian toolkits as well as their rooting in diverse technological modalities suggests divergent principles of techno-economic organization. Tool manufacture appears to be more important in the Northern Ahmarian when compared to its southern counterpart and the relationship between blank and tool production is more intricate. This is certainly reflective of retouch intentionalities that at times substantially interfere with inherited blank shapes and proximal configurations.

Although the attribution and technological characterization of many key Ahmarian sites await systematic re-evaluation, Al-Ansab 1 exhibits clear technological and typological similarities with other sites from the marginal zone such as Boker A (Jones et al. 1983; Monigal 2003), Nahal Nizzana XIII (Davidzon and Goring-Morris 2003; Goring-Morris and Davidzon 2006), the Abu Noshra sites (Phillips 1987, 1988; Becker 2003), Qadesh Barnea (Gilead and Bar-Yosef 1993), or the Ahmarian assemblage from Umm el Tlel (Ploux and Soriano 2003) and thus clearly fall into the southern variant of the techno-complex (Hussain 2015; Parow-Souchon 2020; Richter et al. 2020). Wider techno-economic comparisons within the Southern Ahmarian are generally hampered, however, by the traditional emphasis on type-lists and generic technological characteristics. Yet the extant literature suggests that other Ahmarian sites in the marginal zone share the main features of the basic techno-economic system encountered in Al-Ansab 1. The comprehensive refit evidence from Nahal Nizzana XIII (Davidzon and Goring-Morris 2003; Goring-Morris and Davidzon 2006) is for example consistent with the integrated nature of lithic production proposed for the Early Ahmarian at Al-Ansab 1 and indicates the existence of similarly structured relationships between blank production and tool manufacture. Ferring's (1988) original definition of the Early Ahmarian in the marginal zone based on the distinction between blanks with 'critical morphologies' versus

blank morphologies that are primarily core-related, leading to an internally differentiated spectrum of blanks to be selected for varied tools and functional purposes, is similarly consistent with the lithic evidence from Al-Ansab 1.

A notable and apparently widely shared techno-economic feature in the Southern Ahmarian is the recurrent co-optation of thick core-flank flakes and their preferential transformation into endscrapers as well as the utilization of core tablets as burin or scraper matrices (Ferring 1976: Pl. 7–8; Jones et al. 1983; Goring-Morris 1995; Monigal 2003). According to Saca (2002: 53), a strong linkage between core tablets and large burins is also attested in the central Negev for example (cf. Davidzon and Goring-Morris 2003: 181; Hussain 2015). Monigal (2003: 129) has further noted that in Boker A, 36% of the available secondary products (i.e. flake and core trimming elements) were modified, whereas only 10% of the total pool of laminar blanks were turned into tools. She explicitly states that the larger and more robust blanks were not directly tied to the primary production of targeted blades. Instead, they were preferentially transformed into heavy-duty tools or used as expedient tools, evincing a broadly similar techno-economic logic as observed at Al-Ansab 1. The Boker A evidence – certainly holding a key place for understanding the distinctness of Southern Ahmarian – is also generally consistent with an *économie du débitage* foundation of techno-economic organization (cf. Perlès 1980). An inverse relationship between targeted products and by-product frequencies and their intensity of modification is linked to the marked pre-determination of the central laminar blanks in Southern Ahmarian core reduction systems. This almost ‘preferential’ technical solution conditions tool modification modalities that refrain from substantially interfering with the achieved morphological and technical properties of obtained blanks (cf. Hussain 2015) and produces toolkits that markedly differ from Northern Ahmarian or Levantine Aurignacian tool assemblages.

This being said, compared to other Early Ahmarian open-air sites in the southern Levant, Al-Ansab 1 stands out in terms of raw material management and occupational intensity. The

majority of Ahmarian sites from the marginal zone are interpreted to represent exceptionally ephemeral occupations (cf. Bar-Yosef and Phillips 1977; Marks and Freidel 1977; Marks and Ferring 1988; Gilead and Bar-Yosef 1993; Davidzon and Goring-Morris 2003; Goring-Morris and Davidzon 2006; Phillips 1988; Goring-Morris and Belfer-Cohen 2003; Parow-Souchon 2020), and the treatment of raw materials is normally more conservative, less affluent and tends to be expedient. This interpretation is in agreement with recent zooarchaeological and taphonomic data from Manot Cave in northern Israel (Yeshurun et al. 2021). Generally speaking, raw material procurement in the Levant is assumed to target short distance outcrops or nearby wadi beds with suitable nodules or cobbles (Belfer-Cohen and Goring-Morris 1986: 45; Gilead and Bar-Yosef 1993; Goring-Morris 1995: 4; Belfer-Cohen et al. 2004: 29; Kuhn et al. 2004: 13), even though this estimation is rarely put to the test. Most Southern Ahmarian lithic assemblages are consistent with residential mobility patterns. Artifact densities, sedimentation dynamics, site sizes and toolkit configurations all point to relatively short-term and highly specialized occupations (Marks and Freidel 1977; Marks and Ferring 1988; Henry 1995; Parow-Souchon 2020: 275–292), but no currently known site displays levels of residentiality, site-fidelity and raw material affluence, including premature core discard, comparable to Al-Ansab 1.

Comparative, quantitative data for lithic raw material economies, curation versus expediency, reduction intensities and human mobility within the Early Ahmarian are not yet widely available either. Detailed raw material and curation studies encompassing Initial Upper Paleolithic and Northern Ahmarian layers have so far been conducted only at Üçağızlı cave (Kuhn 2004). Tool curation behavior throughout Üçağızlı's Ahmarian sequence, reflected for example in endscraper reduction values, remains fairly constant and generally indicates reduced raw material conservation and reduction – a pattern broadly consistent with the evidence from Al-Ansab 1. Interestingly, however, the two uppermost Ahmarian layers in Üçağızlı (B and B1–B4) have yielded evidence for pronounced raw material exploitation and site occupation.

Kuhn (2004: 443) concluded that ‘a greater reliance on potentially more costly inland primary flint deposits is associated with apparently more wasteful treatment of tools’ which might be an raw material affluence signature similar to Al-Ansab 1. Kuhn (2004: 444–445) has interpreted the lithic curation data together with evidence for thicker and denser, midden-like occupational layers in the uppermost part of the Ahmarian sequence (B1–B4) as a general shift in provisioning strategies – from a provisioning of individuals associated with less intense, relatively brief occupational events, to provisioning of places tied to the relaxation of raw material costs through object and nodule import (including pre-prepared cores). The latter has resulted in increased raw material availability and predictability and a foraging system reflecting long-distance hunting trips and an expansion of diet breadth (Kuhn 2004).

Albeit deriving from very different site contexts, the data from Üçağızlı and Al-Ansab 1 may point to a larger-scale change in human mobility systems and provisioning strategies in the course of the Early Upper Palaeolithic in the Southern Levant. During the Early Ahmarian, this change seems to have occurred after human groups have consolidated their way of life and acquired detailed ‘landscape knowledge’ (Rockman 2003; Hussain and Floss 2016) on lithologies and animal ecologies and then synergetically adapted their technology, toolkits and movement patterns to the resource affordances of their environment. Since the Southern Ahmarian occupation at Al-Ansab 1 dates to the middle to later phase of the Early Ahmarian (Richter et al. 2020), and it is possible that the unique residentiality and apparently wasteful component of its raw material management simply reflects a more general trend in the evolution of the Early Ahmarian across the Levantine region, in which activity provisioning – and to some extent place provisioning – started to play increasingly important roles.

CONCLUSIONS

Al-Ansab 1 is an Early Ahmarian occupation of unusual intensity close to a highly productive raw material outcrop (URC Ansab). The settlement location, close to high-quality raw material

and ungulate game – either migrating through the Wadi Araba or seeking shelter in the wadi belt – and commanding a wide view over the area, suggests careful selection of the camp location. The site is located at the wettest spot in the Wadi Sabra, and it is only here that freshwater can be found throughout the year, even under dry conditions. The flint-carrying limestone ridge at the back of the site and the wadi flanks simultaneously shelters the site from all but southerly winds, which results in comparatively warm and generally favorable micro-climatic conditions. Raw material and technological data from Al-Ansab 1 corroborate the strategic position of the site in the landscape and reveal a highly adapted techno-economic system of planning and resource scheduling.

The lithic technology of Al-Ansab 1 is oriented towards the production of standardized, narrow-pointed blades for plain use or transformation into el-Wad points. The technical system attests an integrated production of domestic and hunting-related tools and different stages of the operational sequence yield different types of products – ranging from robust, thick flakes to laminar products of varying morphological configuration. These different blanks were selected according to their morphotechnical affordances and transformed into all needed tools. Al-Ansab 1 reflects a classic blank production economy (*économie du débitage*), and structural convergence between blank production and tool production is high. Tool shares are generally low and modification is minimally invasive, emphasizing and reinforcing already achieved blank outlines and properties rather than enforcing novel qualities.

Operational sequence analysis has further shown that all stages of the technological process – from raw material selection and core preparation to core maintenance and tool manufacture – are present at Al-Ansab 1 and differences in raw material management (local vs. non-local) are negligible. The technological analysis reveals that raw material volumes are rarely exploited to their limits and that both cores and tools are discarded before structural depletion. This finding is supported by qualitative and quantitative results from curation analysis, demonstrating that some tools are occasionally reduced intensively. Most tools,

however exhibit short modification sequences with only a single use stage. This general configuration of the toolkit is consistent with the logic of blank production economies, in which tool differentiation is mainly achieved through blank diversification rather than blank transformation. A notable observation concerns the probable division between mobile and stationary tool components, with endscrapers and expedient tool forms on byproducts and CTEs apparently falling into the latter while plain central blades, el-Wad points and specialized blade tool such as truncations and burins falling into the former category.

As shown by the revealed techno-economic trade-offs and curational strategies underpinning the lithic assemblage from Al-Ansab 1, technology must be discussed on various levels of organization. Raw material acquisition and management appears to be relatively expedient and perhaps even wasteful, blank production indicates high levels of planning and is generally curated, while investment in tool production is comparatively low and tool curation does not seem to be a significant locus of technical investment and elaboration. The global articulation of these various levels of organization and their interaction with site choice and raw material affordances at Al-Ansab points to a distinct combination of activity and individual provisioning, yet does not exclude place provisioning as a viable economic option in the later part of the Early Ahmarian as for example evidenced by a few imported and probably prepared cores. In total, raw material economy, technological organization and intra-spatial analysis point to a residential system of mobility where dislocation distance is low-to-medium, while mobility frequency appears exceptionally high.

The difficulty of interpreting the techno-economic signature of Al-Ansab 1 in terms of established measures and concepts of economization, provisioning, and mobility generally suggests that more nuanced concepts, categories, and comparative measures need to be developed and tested in order to understand land-use patterns and economic decision-making in the Early Ahmarian. Future research should pay more attention to the relationships and trade-offs between different technological and behavioral domains (raw material provisioning, blank

production, tool use, etc.) and articulate them with broader ecological and geological/lithological conditions and affordances. Detailed and reproducible raw material studies combined with process-oriented technological analyses are therefore a basic requirement for substantial progress in this area of research. It seems imperative here to combine all available proxies for raw material transport and management, curation, tool use, and lithic technology and to examine their co-adaptation (or not), while avoiding overly simplistic interpretations of the lithic and mobility evidence. In addition, the investigation of Early Ahmarian raw material economies would strongly benefit from a careful reconsideration of Ahmarian seasonality and a more nuanced understanding of key structural constraints operating at the technology-environment interface in the Southern Levant.

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JR: Revisions, Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Fieldwork

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Figure captions:

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Figure 6. Lithology of the Wadi Sabra with identified raw material types projected from two geological source maps (Barjous 2003; Bentor et al. 1970). FRMG = Flint Raw Material Group; URC=Umm Rijam Chert Limestone; AHP/ASP=Al-Hisa Phosphorite/Amman Silicified Limestone; WG= Wadi Umm Ghudran Limestone; WSL= Wadi as Sir Limestone.

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Total Artefacts: 3748

b)

c)

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CO 1

I - Raw material acquisition
angular blocks or tabular sections

II - Initial opening
Preparation of platform

III - Decortification
not specifically

IV - Preparation

Preparation of distal keel and lateral convexities

V - Reduction

VI - Maintenance

VII - Discard

CO 2

CO 3

Production of carinated endscrapers & burins

VIII - Use of large cortical flakes
for endscrapers and burins

VII - Discard
of precores with knapping accidents
from preparation

VII - Discard
of cores with knapping accidents
from reduction

VIII - Use of target blades
as El Wad Points

and production of
other tools*

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